

PERCEIVED VIEW OF MALE FARMERS TOWARDS FEMALE FARM MANAGERS

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture in many societies is considered a male-dominated industry, where female leadership positions are underrepresented. In these societies, male farmers may show conservatism working with/under female leadership due to their perceptions. This study aims to understand the factors and behavioral dynamics influencing male farmers to support and endorse females as farm managers to commend an effective gender-inclusive agricultural community. A multistage sampling technique was employed in selecting 226 male farmers from nine Local Government Areas of the three zones in Niger State. Data collected were subjected to Likert scale analysis and probit regression, to measure the farmers' behavioral dynamics, and factors influencing their support for female farmers respectively. Findings revealed that 82.3% of the farmers are in their active age, with an average household size of 9.2 and 3.2 females in the family. About 73.4% solely own and operate their farm. The farmers expressed optimism regarding the financial independence and family financial support of the female farmers. However, they expressed conservatism in the females' participation and contribution to farmers' associations, critical decision-making, and management of larger farms. They were indifferent regarding the inclusion of the females in the family in on-farm activities. Results of the probit analysis have shown that male farmers' perception towards female farm managers is positive when they are older with demonstrated knowledge and have acquired some training, while household size, farm scale and other jobs exhibited negative influence. The study recommends recognizing the valuable perspective and experience of older farmers and continuous investment in training initiatives.

Keywords: Perception; Gender; Farm manager; Probit regression.

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural development is crucial to feeding the future. More importantly, every available resource must be efficiently utilized to attain this goal. Nigeria has over 68.64 million hectares of agricultural land, out of which about 36.9 million hectares (53.7%) is used as arable land. The Nigerian population as of 2022 was estimated to be 218.54 million with 2.4% annual growth rate. The gender distribution of the population is estimated at 49.5% females and 50.5% males (World Bank,

2022). Share of employment in agriculture, forestry and fishing in total employment constitutes male 45.3% and female 30% (FAOSTAT, 2019). The role of female in agriculture are customarily defined by tasks such as planting, harvesting, processing, and taking care of domestic animals (Baba *et al.*, 2015). The few females that engage in agriculture as farm managers are mostly operating small-scale farming (Gebre *et al.*, 2021; Umunna *et al.* 2021).

Agriculture is embedded in the social and

cultural norms of many societies. In developing countries, these societies consider the sector as male-dominated, where female leadership positions are underrepresented (Rahman *et al.*, 2020). Despite these gender imbalances in the agricultural sector, some females have demonstrated competence and success in the aspect of farm management by breaking through the stereotypes and getting the necessary support from the society (FAO, 2011). Some of these successes are recorded in Ghana (Duncan, 1997), in Bangladesh (Rahman, *et al.*, 2020; Mobarok *et al.*, 2021), in Uganda (Wilcox *et al.*, 2021), in India (Agarwal, 2020), and in Kenya (Onyalo, 2019). Nevertheless, some key challenges kept resurfacing particularly on the perceptions towards females as farm managers in communities of developing countries. The male farmers may have reservations about working with or under female leadership due to their perceptions, which are mostly shaped by believes that females may lack physical strength, stamina or skills to effectively manage farms. These believes have become strong leading to confirmation bias. In many societies, the effort of females is deliberately looked at and interpreted based on remembered information that aligned with current believes, thereby ignoring anything that go against that believe even when the effort shows potential positive impact in the society. Hence, females face challenges that not only hinder their active participation into the sector but also reduce their productivity as well.

Decision-making is an integral function in farm management, where households, the primary societal unit is where decisions are commonly made, and responsibilities allocated among family members (French, 1995). Distinctively in developing countries, decision-making role predominantly rests with the male household head, wielding significant influence on the food security, health, and

overall livelihood of all the household members (Alemu *et al.*, 2000). Therefore, the views of the male farmers are a proxy of the community's view. Knowledge on their perception could be used to generate a new narrative promoting a gender-inclusive norm. Hence, comprehensively exploring the perception of male household heads towards female farm managers in society is imperative. This is essential for enhancing the understanding of how to effectively support female farm managers and promote increase female participation in the rural communities of developing countries. This study intends to clarify how the male household farmers interpret scenarios where females assume role of farm managers, emphasizing on the perceptions and other factors that shape the male farmers' willingness to endorse and support female farm managers. This will identify potential biases, stereotypes and other gender related challenges that may need to be addressed to encourage female participation. The study is aligned with the research objective of the research grant from Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TetFund) on "Gender Dynamics in Farm Management". Its specific focus is to identify the motivating factors that influence female farm managers and to pinpoint the unique constraints they encounter, with an aim to contribute to the reduction of gender gap in farm management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The research was carried out in Niger State of Nigeria. The State has the largest land area in in the country covering an approximate land area of 76,363.9km². Niger State has an estimated population of 5.56 million with 3.5% annual growth rate, and gender distribution of males 50.7% and females 49.3%. The State is considered an agrarian State given the significant proportion of the

population (85 %) that are engaged in farming and other agricultural activities (Niger State Bureau of Statistics, 2012). The State has three ecological zones including Zone 1 (South), Zone 2 (East) and Zone 3(North-West). Each of these zones is distinct with different cultures, and agricultural activities.

Data collection

A multistage sampling technique was employed for this study. In the first stage, the three ecological zones of the State were purposefully selected, followed by the second stage where three Local Government Areas (LGAs) from each zone were randomly chosen, resulting in a total of 9 LGAs. These LGAs encompass Zone 1: Agaie, Bida, and Mokwa; Zone 2: Bosso, Paikoro, and Suleja; and Zone 3: Borgu, Kontagora, and Wushishi. The third stage involved the random selection of 226 male farm managers engaged in crop, livestock, and fish farming. A structured questionnaire was administered to collect information on their socioeconomic characteristics, farm management activities, and challenges. Additionally, Likert scale responses were obtained to gauge their perceptions on female farm managers in terms of decision-making, performance, finance, capability, interactions with other farmers, and overall contribution to the community.

Data analysis

The initial step involved presenting descriptive statistics of the respondents, providing insights from their socioeconomic status to their engagement in farm and farm management activities. Furthermore, a 5-point Likert psychometric scale, with values 0 (never), 1 (rarely), 2 (sometime), 3 (often), and 4 (always), was utilized to gauge the perception of male farmers towards female farm managers. Following this, a probit regression analysis was conducted to elucidate the impact of socioeconomic factors and farm

management activities on the willingness of male farm managers to support/endorse female farmers in the study area.

Probit Model Specification

The probit model assumes that the dependent variable, the Y_i index, follows a standard normal distribution. The probability that Y_i takes the value of 1 (success or failure occurs) is given by the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the standard normal distribution. The model is specified as:

$$P(Y_i = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ik}) \quad (1)$$

when

$$P(Y_i = 1) = \text{is the probability of success}$$

Φ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function.

$X_{i1}, X_{i2} \dots X_{ik}$ are the independent variables

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2 \dots \beta_k$ are the coefficient to be estimated

$$\Phi(z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^z e^{-\frac{1}{2}t^2} dt$$

Here: $O(z)$ = probability that a standard normal random variable is less than or equal to z

e = the base of natural logarithm. $n = 3.14159$.

t = Variable of integration.

The dependent variable specifies the code zero (0) when the male farmer does not support female farmer, and code 1 supports female farmer. The independent variables in this study include age, household size, other jobs, farming experience, years of education, farm scale value, belonging to farmer associations, numbers of family in the family, and contact with extension agent. The likelihood function within the probit model is based on the presumption that the dependent variable follows a Bernoulli

distribution. The likelihood function represents the probability of observing the actual outcome (0 and 1 of the dependent variable) given the parameters in the model.

$$L(\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k) = \prod P(Y_i = y_i)^{y_i} (1 - P(Y_i = y_i))^{1 - y_i}$$

Where y_i is the observed outcome (0 or 1) for observation “ i ”. The coefficients specify the impact of the independent variable on the chances of the occurring event.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socioeconomics characteristics

Table 1 presents the socioeconomic characteristics of the male farmers. On average, the farmers are about 40 years old with slightly over 82% less than 51 years of age. Implying that the majority of them are in their active age. A similar observation was seen in Baba *et al.* (2021). The average household size of the farmers is about 9 persons with 31% having over 10 persons/household. The minimum and maximum number of females in the household

are 0 and 14 respectively. On average, there are about 3 females in the household. This factor is particularly important as it can influence the perception of the male farmers towards female farm managers. Accordingly, the farmers (on average) have attained about 11.6 years of formal education which is almost equivalent to a secondary school certificated. The level of education is principal to adoption of new technologies (Muhammed-lawal *et al.* 2009) and or endorsement of female farmers. As expected, there are more married farmers (87.2%) than the single farmers given the average age of the farmers. Majority of the farmers (61.1%) have a secondary source from daily wage (35.8%), salary (23.9%) and pensioner (1.3%). Only 38.9% were strictly into farming.

Table 1: Socioeconomic characteristics of the male farmers

	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean
Age	>50	40	17.7	40
	=50	186	82.3	
Household size	>10	70	31	9.2
	=10	156	69	
Females in family		0 (min)	14 (max)	3.2
Education (formal)	Years	0 (min)	22 (max)	11.6
Marital status	Single	29	12.8	
	Married	197	87.2	
Main occupation	Daily wage	81	35.8	
	Pensioner	3	1.3	
	Salary employee	54	23.9	
	Farming only	88	38.9	

Source: Field survey data 2023

Farm Statistics and Activities

Farms: the male farmers are actively engaged in crop, fish and livestock farming. The distribution of the farmers according to farm types is depicted in Figure 1. Majority of the farmers (71.2%) are crop farmers cultivating

crops like maize, rice, groundnut, soybean, guinea corn, yam, cowpea, sorghum, cassava, millet, sesame, melon seed and sweet potato. The livestock farmers constitute 17.3% of the male farmers rearing cattle, sheep, goats and birds (poultry), while the remaining 11.5% of

the farmers are into fish farming including fingerlings, catfish and tilapia fish production. This result implies that most of the farmers prefer crop farming which is low risk compared to fish and livestock farming.

Farm ownership: the farm ownership status of the male farmers is presented in Table 2. The ownership is grouped into sole owner, partnership and employed as manager. The pooled survey result shows that 73.5% of the

farmers solely own and operate their farms, 22.6% into partnership and 4% are farm managers employed by farm owners. The ownership status on each farm also shows sole owner being the major status followed by partnership and then employed as manager. The ownership distribution in these farm shows that the farmers enjoy autonomous decision-making authority in the management of their farms.

Figure 1: Distribution of the farmers by farm type

Source: Field survey data 2023

Table 2: Farm ownership different farm

	Sole owner		Partnership		Employed as manager	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Crop farm	126	55.8	33	14.6	2	0.9
Fish farm	11	4.9	9	4	6	2.7
Livestock	29	12.8	9	4	1	0.4
Pooled	166	73.5	51	22.6	9	4

Source: Field survey data 2023

Land size: the average land size owned by the male farmers in the study area is about 3.6 ha with a minimum of 0.02 ha and a maximum of 50 ha (presented in Table 3). It was observed in the survey that the majority of the fish and livestock farmers owned relatively smaller pieces of land compared to the crop farmers. This negates the result in FAO (2019) which

reported male farmers having a 1.5 ha land size in Nigeria. This disparity could be because of the comparative advantage Niger State has in terms of land area compared to other state in the country.

Farm scale: for unified comparison and analysis, this study measured farm scale as value (Naira) of production volume because of

the diverse agricultural products engaged in by the farmers. According to the result in Table 3, the mean farm scale value of the is about N6.2 million implying that the vast majority of the farmers operate relatively medium scale farms. the least and maximum scale values observed are N64,000 and N162 million respectively.

Farming experience: on average, the male

farmers had about 18 years of farming experience. This result is consistent with Muhammed *et al.* (2021). The least and highest farming experience recorded are 1 and 50 years respectively. This result suggests there are ample number of new entries into the agricultural farming by the males in the study area.

Table 3: land size, farm scale and farming experience

	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Size of land(s) owned (ha)	3.6	5.4	0.02	50
Farm scale value (₦ 000)	6,224	18,500	64	162,000
Farming experience (years)	18.2	11.3	1	50

Source: Field survey data 2023

Figure 2a

Member farmers association

Figure 2b

Trained

Figure 2c

Contact with extension agent

The study revealed that very few of the male farmers were member of farmer’s associations, with about 75% indicating non-membership (Figure 2a). This suggest that there is potential gap in support network among male farmers. This finding is consistent with Kinkingninhoun *et al.* (2020) but in contrast with Kolapo *et al.* (2020). Additionally, the findings revealed that about 45% of the male farmers had received at least a form of training (Figure 2b), indicating a moderate level of exposure to farm management education and skills development. Moreover, majority of the male farmers, 74%, reported having contact with

extension agents (Figure 2c), implying a relatively high level of interaction with agricultural extension services. Similar result was also found in Ikoyo-Eweto *et al.* (2023).

Perception of Male Farmers towards

Female Farm Managers

The male farmers were asked to rate series of statements gauged by a 5-point Likert psychometric scale, with values ranged from 0 (never) to 4 (always). Their responses were analyzed and presented in Figure 3 – response from individual crop, fish and livestock farms, and Table 4 – the detailed pooled response of the male farmers.

Figure 3: Perception of male farmers according to farm type
Source: Field survey data 2023

Figure 3 shows the perception towards females as farm managers by the crop, fish and livestock male farmers in three farms. The mean responses for each farm on the 12 statements were analyzed to differentiate variations in their attitude. In comparison to the crop and fish farmers, the livestock farmers showed higher positive response in statements regarding spouse participation makes farming interesting (2.5), teaching spouse farming (2.3), respecting spouse's decision-making (1.95), believing female can operate large scale farms (1.6), allowing female in the family to participate in farm (2.15), community appreciation of female farmers (2.7), and recognition of their success in farm management (2.0). On the other hand, fish farmers exhibited higher positive response regarding female participation (1.46) and contribution (1.54) to farmers associations,

compared to the crop farmers (1.4 and 1.4) and livestock (1.3 and 1.2). The crop farmers exhibited higher positive responses in comparison to fish and livestock farmers regarding the financial independence (2.6) and support to spouse (2.6). In summary, the livestock farmers tend to have higher positive response to more of the statements towards female farmers compared to the crop and fish farmers, implying that the males recognize more roles played by females in livestock farming than other farms. This is in consonant with Curry (1996) who opined that women contribute to livestock farming than crop farming. These can be attributed to practical factors such as requirement of small capital/resources, limited access to other resources (e.g. land), and cultural factor (Mollel and Mtenga, 2000).

Table 4: Pooled perceive view of male farmers towards female farm managers.

Perception on female farmers	Percentage (%)					Mean	Rank
	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always		
Female participation in association meeting	31.4	23.0	28.3	11.1	6.2	1.38	12 th
Females contribute to the association	31.4	22.1	27.4	12.1	6.6	1.41	11 th
Spouse participation makes farming interesting	10.2	23.5	27.4	17.1	21.7	2.17	5 th
I teach my spouse how to farm	13.1	23.5	29.7	9.3	23.9	2.06	6 th
My spouse makes excellent farm decisions	13.3	25.7	35.4	14.1	11.1	1.85	9 th
They can manage large scale farms	17.1	35.8	27.9	12.1	6.2	1.55	10 th
Females in the family participate in farm	7.1	16.8	53.1	8.9	14.2	2.06	6 th
Females can do well in farm	8.4	31.9	31.4	3	11.1	1.91	8 th
Financial support to spouse	4.9	15.0	34.1	5	26.6	2.48	3 rd
Financial independence	3.1	13.7	34.5	8	27.9	2.57	2 nd
Communities appreciates female farmers	3.1	15.9	29.7	6	32.7	2.62	1 st
Community needs more female farmers	4.0	<u>31.0</u>	24.3	6	18.1	2.20	4 th

Source: *Field survey data 2023*

The pooled response of the male farmers is presented in Table 4. The responses were ranked and grouped into optimistic, indecisive and conservative. The optimistic group – are the highest responses supporting female farm managers; the indecisive group – are those responses indifferent on whether to support or not; and the conservative group – are responses giving less support. Three statements ranked 1st, 2nd, and 3rd were the most optimistic responses. The inference to this is that despite all odds, some the male farmers (with response

between ‘Sometimes’ and ‘Often’) recognize and appreciate the financial independence and support from the female farm managers. Four statements fall under the indecisive group (ranked 4th, 5th, and 6th) where the male farmers responded to statements such as the need for female farmers in the community, participation of spouses in farming making farming interesting, male farmers (husbands) teaching their spouse(s) how to farm and the participation of females of the family in farm. Out of the twelve statements, five statements

ranked from 8th to 12th were the most conservative response from the male farmers. The implication of this is that the response to almost half of the statements asked, are less likely to support or endorse females as being good farm managers in terms of decision-making, maintaining larger farms and positively participating in farmers associations.

Probit Regression Analysis

The perception of male farmers (household heads) may differ based on their age,

experience, education, training, location/culture, household size, gender structure in the family and many other factors. The probit regression analysis predicts the likelihood of the perceive view of the male farmers on whether they will support or endorse the idea of females as farm managers based on their socioeconomic and farming statistics. The result in Table 5 provides insight on the factors influencing the support/endorsement of female farm managers by the male farmers.

Table 5: Probit analysis on perceive view of male farmers towards female Farmers

Support	Coef.	Std.Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
Age	1.0050	0.5479	1.83	0.067	-0.0688	2.0788
Scale value	0.1712	0.1024	-1.67	0.095	-0.3719	0.0296
Other jobs	0.5921	0.3032	-1.95	0.051	-1.1863	0.0021
Trained	0.5639	0.3043	1.85	0.064	-0.0325	1.1603
Household size	0.4526	0.2479	1.83	0.068	-0.9386	0.0333
constant	0.5191	2.2387	0.23	0.817	-4.9068	3.8686
<i>LR Chi²(5) = 12.24</i>					<i>Number of obs = 220</i>	
<i>Pseudo R² = 0.0408</i>					<i>Prob > Chi² = 0.0316</i>	

Source: Field survey data 2023

According to the result in Table 5, **age** is a significant factor influencing the decision of male farmers on supporting females as farm managers. A year increase in the average age of the farmers is associated with a 1.005 increase in the odds of the male farmers supporting female farm managers. In other words, if two farmers have same farm scale value, same household size, training, and have similar status on other jobs, the odds of the older farmer endorsing female farmers is about 1.005 times higher. Similarly, being trained is positively associated with supporting female

farmers. For example, with other factors remaining constant, the odds of the trained male farmer endorsing females as good farm managers are about 0.6 times higher than the male farmer who is not trained. Contrarily, farm scale, other jobs and household size present negative relationship with male farmers endorsing females as farm managers. These results explain that a unit increase in farm scale value is associated with about 0.1712 decrease in the odds of supporting female farmers. In other words, farmers with smaller farm scales are more

likely to support female farmers compared to those with larger scales who are about 0.2 times less likely to support. Conversely, having other jobs other than farming have negative impact on the support of female farmers by the male farmers. With males who are majorly head of household and having multiple sources of income could be reluctant to support females in the family to engage in farming since he can provide for the family. A one-unit increase in household size of the male farmers is associated with a 0.4526 decrease in the odds of supporting female farmers. This implies that the odds of that the males with larger household size endorsing females as good farm managers are about 0.45 times lower than the male farmers with smaller household size. Other factors including years of education, contact with extension agent, belonging to farmer associations, and numbers of family in the family were dropped from the result by stepwise regression command used which only allow significant factors to be displayed. The absence of these factors does not mean they are not important in influencing the male farmers' decisions, but rather are not statistically significant at 0.1 alpha level.

C O N C L U S I O N A N D R E C O M M E N D A T I O N S

This study is paramount to fostering gender-inclusive agricultural system by identifying barriers to the acceptance or support for female

farm managers in Niger State of Nigeria. The perceive view of male farmers towards female farmers was analyzed: firstly, by ascertaining the rating of the male farmers based on the female farmers' farm management skills, financing, commitment, contributions to family and the overall community; and secondly by determining factors that can influence male farmers decision to support female farmers. Conclusively, the following were deduced: the male farmers were optimistic about the ability of the female farmers in areas such as financial independence and support to family; they were more conserved in aspects such as critical decision making, management of large-scale farm, participation and contribution to farmers association; their response was indecisive on aspects such as including and/or teaching their spouse in the farming decision and the participation of females in the family. Older male farmers and the farmers who had training are more likely to support and endorse female farmers. Contrary to this, farmers with larger farm scales, having other jobs and larger household sizes were less likely to support or endorse female farmers. The study recommends recognizing the valuable experience and perspectives of older farmers, and a continuous investment in training of farmers itemizing more gender-inclusive initiatives. Further research should be considered tailoring initiatives to address concerns of the specific groups on supporting female farmers.

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